

ORGANIC FUNGICIDES. PART II. ON CERTAIN
ETHERS OF CRESOTINIC ESTERS

BY A. B. SEN AND K. C. JOSHI

Several esters and ether-esters of cresotinic acids have been prepared.

Cavill, Vincent and Gibson (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1947, **66**, 175) observed that esters and ether-esters of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (*ibid.*, 1947, **66**, 274) possess good fungistatic activity. The present work was therefore undertaken to prepare analogous esters and ether-esters of *ortho*- and *meta*-cresotinic acids, which may also be expected to possess similar fungistatic activity.

The esters of *o*-cresotinic acid have been obtained by Schotten-Baumann's reaction by treating the acid chloride (obtained by the action of phosphorus pentachloride on the acid, suspended in petrol ether) with an excess of the requisite alcohol (Anschutz, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 223; Ansch, Schroeder, Weber and Ansprach, *Annalen*, 1908 **346**, 342). The esters of *m*-cresotinic acid have been obtained by Fischer's method by refluxing the parent acid with an excess of the requisite alcohol containing 3% hydrochloric acid gas as a catalyst. (Behal, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1908, *iv*, **3**, 730; Pinner, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 2938).

The method used for the preparation of the ethers was an adoption of that described by Cavill and Gibson (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1947, **66**, 274) who obtained these ethers by refluxing the sodium derivative of the hydroxy-esters with the appropriate *n*-alkyl iodide in absolute alcohol. The sodium derivative of the cresotinic acid-alkyl ester itself was obtained by the addition of the ester to an equivalent quantity of sodium ethoxide, dissolved in excess of absolute alcohol.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Oxy-3-methylbenzoyl Chloride.—2-Oxy-3-methylbenzoyl chloride was prepared by the method of Anschutz (*loc. cit.*) and Ansch *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) by treating *o*-cresotinic acid (100 g.) with PCl_5 (165 g.) in petrol-ether (250 c.c.). The petrol-ether and POCl_3 were removed and the residual liquid distilled under reduced pressure. It is a pale yellow liquid, b.p. $202^\circ/5\text{mm}$. yield 102 g. (91.1% of theory) (Anschutz *et al.*, *loc. cit.* report m.p. 28°).

Esters of *o*-Cresotinic Acid.—These esters were obtained by Schotten-Baumann's reaction by treating 2-oxy 3-methylbenzoyl chloride (1 mol.) with excess of the requisite anhydrous alcohol (4 mols.). The excess of the alcohol was removed, the residual liquid washed with cold 20% caustic soda solution and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether removed, and the residual liquid distilled under reduced pressure. The following compounds have been obtained.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Reactants.	Yield.	Boiling point obs.	Analysis.	
				Found.	Calc.
(1) 2-Oxy 3-methyl <i>isopropylbenzoate</i>	Acid chloride (20g.) <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol (35 c.c.)	15 g. 68.0%	$194^\circ/5\text{ mm}$.	C, 67.68% H, 7.35	68.04% 7.22
(2) 2-Oxy 3-methyl <i>n</i> -butylbenzoate	Acid chloride (25 g.) <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol (50 c.c.)	22 72.2	$175/7$	C, 68.76 H, 7.71	69.23 7.69

Besides, 2-oxy-3-methyl methylbenzoate and 2-oxy 3-methyl ethylbenzoate were also prepared and their boiling points were found to be the same as reported by Claisen and Eisleb (*Annalen*, 1913, 401, 82) and Anschutz *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Esters of m-Cresotinic Acid.—The two esters of *m*-cresotinic acid, 2-oxy-4-methyl methylbenzoate and 2-oxy-4-methyl ethylbenzoate, were obtained by Fischer's method by refluxing the acid with the requisite alcohol in presence of 3% hydrochloric acid gas. Their boiling points were in agreement with those reported by Biedermann (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 324) and Pinner (*loc. cit.*).

Ether-esters of Cresotinic Acids.—These compounds were obtained by refluxing for 4 hours, the sodium salt of the cresotinic acid-alkyl ester (1 mol.) with the required alkyl iodide (20% in excess) in absolute ethyl alcohol. The sodium salt was prepared by adding sodium (1 mol.) to excess of absolute alcohol and treating the sodium ethoxide, thus obtained, with the required ester (1 mol.). The excess of the alcohol was distilled off, the residual reaction mixture treated with water to dissolve the sodium iodide and extracted with ether. It was dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether removed, and the residual liquid distilled under reduced pressure. The following ether-esters have been obtained.

TABLE II

Compounds. [B = benzoate]	B.p.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	C a r b o n		H y d r o g e n	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
(1) 2-Ethoxy 3-methyl methyl-B	154°/4 mm.	53.8%	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	67.74%	68.04%	7.92%	7.22%
(2) 2-Methoxy 3-methyl ethyl-B	145°/25	51.6	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	67.69	68.04	7.12	7.22
(3) 2-Ethoxy 3-methyl ethyl-B	148°/5	54.1	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	68.84	69.23	7.58	7.69
(4) 2-Methoxy 3-methyl isopropyl-B	135°/5	62.2	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂	68.93	69.23	7.44	7.69
(5) 2-Ethoxy 3-methyl isopropyl-B	125°/5	43.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂	69.88	70.26	8.04	8.11
(6) 2-Methoxy 3-methyl <i>n</i> -butyl-B	162°/5	74.9	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ O ₂	69.94	70.26	8.06	8.11
(7) 2-Ethoxy 3-methyl <i>n</i> -butyl-B	168°/8	66.6	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂	70.96	71.16	8.41	8.47
(8) 2-Ethoxy 4-methyl methyl-B	140°/10	76.1	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	67.92	68.04	7.14	7.22
(9) 2-Methoxy 4-methyl ethyl-B	152°/7	74.2	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	67.88	68.04	7.26	7.22
(10) 2-Ethoxy 4-methyl ethyl-B	156°/5	86.5	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂	69.13	69.23	7.56	7.69